

TILSHUNOSLIK TARIXIGA BIR NAZAR**Xodjiyev Mironshox Azamatovich****Buxoro davlat universitetining Pedagogika instituti talabasi**<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6589411>

ANNOTATSIYA: Mazkur maqolada tilshunoslik haqida ma'lumot, uning kelib chiqishi, rivojlanishi hamda tilshunoslikning tarrahiy topishiga o'z hissasini qushgan olimlar haqida aytib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: tilshunoslik, terminlar, lingvistika, amaliy tilshunoslik.

Tilshunoslik yoki lingvistika tillarni o'rganuvchi fandır. Tilshunoslikning amaliy va nazariy turlari mavjud bo'lib, nazariy tilshunoslik tilning strukturasi (grammatikasi) va uning ma'nosi (semantikasini) o'rganadi. Grammatika – morfologiya (so'zlarning tuzilishi va o'zgarishi), sintaksis (so'zlarning iboralarga va gaplarga biriktrilish qoidalari) va fonologiya (tilni abstrakt tovushlar yordamida o'rganish) fanlarini qamrab oladi. Amaliy tilshunoslik, asosan, tilshunoslikda o'rganilgan nazariy bilimlarni amaliyotda qo'llash bilan shug'ullanadi. Amaliy tilshunoslik tarkibiga xorijiy tillarni o'rganish va o'rgatish, tarjima, nutq terapiyasi va nutq patologiyasi kabi fanlar kiradi.

Tilshunoslik, lingvistika – til haqidagi, uning ijtimoiy tabiati, vazifasi, ichki tuzilishi, tasnifi, muayyan tillarning amal qilish (faoliyat) qonunlari, tarixiy taraqqiyoti haqidagi fan. Maqsadi, vazifasi va shu kabi ko'ra, tilshunoslikning bir necha yo'nalishlari (sohalari) bor: umumiy tilshunoslik – tilni umuman insonga xos hodisa sifatida o'rganuvchi, asosiy vazifasi dunyo tillariga xos eng umumiy belgixususiyatlarni aniqlash va yoritish bo'lgan soha, xususiy tilshunoslik – ayrim bir til belgixususiyatlarini o'rganuvchi soha; amaliy tilshunoslik – tildan foydalanish bilan aloqador amaliy masalalarni (eksperimental fonetika, leksikografiya, lingvostatistika, transkripsiya, transliteratsiya va boshqalar) hal qilish metodlarini ishlab chiquvchi yo'nalish; matematik lingvistika, strukturaviy tilshunoslik, kiyosiy-tarixiy tilshunoslik va boshqa paralingvistika, etnolingvistika, psixolingvistika, sotsiolingvistika kabi sohalar so'zlovchi (shaxs)ning jamiyatdagi faoliyati bilan aloqador til xususiyatlarini o'rganadi.

Mazkur yo'nalishlardan tashqari tilshunoslikning har bir tildagi muayyan sathlar va birliklarni o'rganuvchi ko'plab tarmoq va bo'limlari bor: semasiologiya til birliklari ma'nolarini o'rganadi; fonetika va fonologiya tilning tovush qurilishini tekshiradi; leksikologiya va frazeologiya tilning lug'aviy materialini tadqiq etadi. So'z yasalishining tadqiqot obyekti so'zlarning yasalish usullari va ushbu usullarning mahsuldorligi bo'lsa, grammatika (morfologiya va sintaksis) so'z o'zgarishlarini va so'zlarning gaplar va so'z birikmalari sifatida birikishi qonuniyatlarini o'rganadi. Tilshunoslikning har bir bo'limida yanada kichikroq (maydaroq) maxsus bo'limchalar bo'lishi mumkin. Masalan, leksikologiya doirasida onomastika bo'limchasi bo'lib, u, o'z navbatida, antroponimika, toponimika va boshqalarga bo'linadi. Muayyan tilning hududiy farklanishi (differentsiatsiyasi)ni dialektologiya o'rganadi. Mazkur bo'limlarning har birida tilning hozirgi ahvoli va uning tarixiy taraqqiyoti tadqiq etiladi (qarang, diaxroniya, sinxroniya). Jahon tillari, ularning oilalari va guruxlarini o'rganuvchi Tilshunoslik tarmoqlari: arabistika (arabhunoslik), germanshunoslik, turkiyshunoslik, slavyanshunoslik, finugorshunoslik va boshqa tillarning o'zaro ta'sirlashuvi, yordamchi xalqaro tillarni yaratish nazariyasi va amaliyoti, shuningdek, bir tildan ikkinchi tilga tarjima qilish muammolarini interlingvistika va tarjima nazariyasi o'rganadi.

Tilshunoslikfan sifatida ona tili va xorijiy tillarni o'rganishda, terminologiyani ishlab chiqish va takomillashtirishda, lisoniy matnlarni ilmiy sharhlashda, mashina tarjimasida muhim ahamiyatga ega; mavjud va xayoliy narsalar (moddiylik va g'oyaviylik)ning o'zaro aloqadorligi muammolarini hal qilish, ijtimoiy ongini va ijtimoiy mavjudot bo'lmish insonning o'zini to'g'ri tushunish uchun nazariy xulosalar chiqarishga imkon berdi. Til va tafakkurning, lisoniy va mantiqiy birlik (kattalik)larning o'zaro aloqasi muammosi tilshunoslik va falsafa tomonidan baravar, bir vaqtning o'zida o'rganiladi. Asosiy lingvistik metodlar sifatida tavsifiy (qiyosiy, konfrontativ, kontrastiv, tipologik), tarixiy (qiyosiy-tarixiy, komparativ) va normativ-stilistik (me'yoriy-uslubiy) metodlarni ko'rsatish mumkin. Tilshunoslikda yana maxsus tadqiqot usullari – lisoniy hodisalarni kuzatish, lisoniy eksperiment, lingvistik modellashtirish, lingvistik talqin usullari ham mavjud. Tilshunoslik falsafa va filologiya fanlari tutashgan chegarada paydo bo'lgan.

O'zbek tilshunosligi tarixi Mahmud Koshg'ariy va Zamaxshariylarning izlanishlaridan boshlanib, uzoq tarixiy taraqqiyot yo'lini bosib o'tdi. 15-asrdan 20-asr 20-yillarigacha o'zbek tilini o'rganishning amaliy jihatlariga alohida e'tibor berildi, ko'plab ikki tilli (o'zbekcha-forscha,

o'zbekcha-turkcha, o'zbekcha-ruscha va aksincha tartibda) lug'atlar tuzildi. Tilshunoslikning leksikologiya va leksikografiya bo'limlari rivojlandi. O'zbek tilini hozirgi ma'noda o'rganish 20-asrning 20-yillaridan boshlangan. Sho'ro davrida olib borilgan til siyosati, rus tilining jamiyatdagi mavqeyini haddan ziyod oshirib ko'rsatish oqibatida tilni, til hodisalarini o'rganish, tavsif va tadqiq etishda (ayniqsa, o'zbek tili grammatikasini o'rganishda) muayyan kamchilik va nuqsonlarga yo'l qo'yilgan bo'lsa-da, o'zbek Tilshunoslik rivojlanib, ma'lum yutuqlarga erishdi. O'zbek tilshunoslik rivojiga Fitrat, K.Ramazon, Otajon Hoshim, S.Ibrohimov, Olim Usmon, Z.Ma'rufov, Faxri Kamol, A.G'ulomov, F.Abdullayev, Sh.Shoabdurag'monov, G'Abdurahmonov, A.Rustamov, M.Asqarova, X.Doniyorov, Sh.Shukurov, Sh.Rahmatullayev, M.Mirtojiev, E.Begmatov kabi olimlarimiz, rus tilshunoslaridan Ye.D.Polivanov, A.K.Borovkov, K.K.Yudaxin, A.N.Kononov, A.M.Shcherbak, V.V.Reshetov va boshqa katta xissa qo'shdilar. O'zbekistonda Tilshunoslik muammolari O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi Alisher Navoiy nomidagi Til va adabiyot instituti, shuningdek, oliy o'quv yurtlarining tilni o'rgatish bilan bog'liq kafedralari tomonidan o'rganiladi, maxsus "O'zbek tili va adabiyoti" jurnali nashr etiladi.

Ушбу мақолада ўқув луғатларининг умумий луғатлардан нафақат ҳажми, балки ундаги сўзларнинг танланиш мезонлари, луғат қисмларининг таркиби, жойлашуви – мегаструктураси билан ҳам фарқланиши, синоним ўқув луғатлар луғат мақоласи таркибида лексикографик пометалар (турли қисқартмалар, белгилар)га кам ўрин берилганлиги муҳокама қилинади.¹

This article is dedicated to the research of Adjusted meanings of Moral-spiritual concept defining units in the Uzbek language. And also analyzed the semantic analysis of grammatical shape lexemes of specialized meaning and provide a corresponding recommendation for lexicographical practice in the Uzbek language is one of the actual challenges of linguistics as today's challenge.²

¹ Гуландом Мирханова. (2022). СИНОНИМ СЎЗЛАР ЎҚУВ ЛУҒАТИНИНГ УМУМИЙ ТУЗИЛИШИ. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(2), 172–178. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/90>

² Gulbahor, T. (2016). Adjusted Meanings of Moral-Spiritual Concept Defining Units. *ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies*, 5(7), 40-45.

Корпус лингвистикасида семантик разметка, унинг теглар тизими, тег категориялари, семантик теглаш муаммолари, кўпмаънолилик ва омонимлик муаммосини ечиш масаласига оид қатор тадқиқотлар вужудга келган.³

The article discusses the research methods of Uzbek language syntax. In Uzbek linguistics, syntactic phenomena have been studied in detail since the 1930s, and several syntactic theories have emerged in this regard.⁴

The article examines the first dictionary in the Turkish language Mahmud Kashgaris “Devonu lugotit turk” in terms of a dictionary in accordance with the traditions of world lexicography and argues that it is the first appearance of modern complex dictionaries in the Turkish (Uzbek) language.⁵

Now studying scientific heritage, socio-political activities and acquaintance youth charity of our above-stated ancestors is considered one of the main urgent objectives of the modern intellectuals.⁶

This article covers the main place of small business and business in today's market economy. Including scientifically analyzed the development of small business and business, and the legal basis, at this time financially support small business and business, the latter is amended and the rules for this branch of national legislation are added.⁷

Мамлакатимиз тараққиётининг янги босқичида жамият ҳаётининг асосий негизи бўлмиш оилалар барқарор муҳитини мустаҳкамлаш ва бу масалаларда хотин-қизларнинг ўрни ва аҳамияти ошириш долзарб аҳамият касб этмоқда. Юртимиз аҳолисининг тенг

³ Ахмедова, Д. (2020). Семантик разметка тизимида тег гуруҳлари. *Oriental Art and Culture*, (III), 440-444.

⁴ Ergashevna, Y. N. (2021). ON METHODS OF RESEARCH OF UZBEK LANGUAGE SYNTAX. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(11), 22-28.

⁵ Bakhriddinova, B. M. (2020). “DEVONU LUGOTIT TURK” AS A FIRST VIEW OF MODERN COMPLEX EDUCATIONAL DICTIONARIES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 981-985.

⁶ Tolibjonovich, M. T. (2021). EASTERN RENAISSANCE AND ITS CULTURAL HERITAGE: THE VIEW OF FOREIGN RESEARCHERS. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(05), 211-215.

⁷ Tolibjonovich, Madumarov T., and Gulomjonov O. R. Ogli. "Lombard Microcredit Organization Its Concept and Its Importance Today." *JournalNX*, vol. 6, no. 10, 2020, pp. 109-111.

ярмига яқинроғини ташкил этадиган хотин-қизлар жамиятнинг барча соҳаларида самарали фаолият юритмоқда.⁸

In this article are given the importance, role, types of the family in modern society. Its development from ancient times till present is widely described in this article.⁹

The widespread introduction of new pedagogical technologies in teaching students of higher educational institutions and the effective use of innovative technologies are the main support for improving the quality of education.¹⁰

The article describes in detail the basics of translation theory, the object of research, and the methods of analysis of translation theory. Opinions on the importance of translation among different peoples, the concept of translation, and its types are discussed. However, various examples of translation types are given.¹¹

The aim of the present study was to determine whether an association exists between the duration of menopause and the age of menopause onset, and the differences in bone mineral density (BMD) in postmenopausal women.¹²

This article analyzes how Somerset Maugham's short story "A Friend in Need" skillfully reflects the power and value of true friendship using ethical concepts such as goodness, kindness, justice, and compassion, which are sacred to each of us.¹³

⁸ Мадумарова Зиёдахон. (2022). ЯНГИЛАНАЁТГАН ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ГЕНДЕР МУАММОЛАРИНИ БАРТАРАФ ЭТИШДА АХЛОҚИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРИНИНГ ЎРНИ. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6569712>

⁹ Nasriddinovich, A. A. (2020). THE FEATURES OF APPEARING FAMILY IN MODERN SOCIETY. *European science review*, (3-4), 69-72.

¹⁰ Jamoliddinovich, U. B. (2022). FUNDAMENTALS OF EDUCATION QUALITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429*, 11(01), 149-151.

¹¹ Gafurovna, R. Z. (2021). Translation Theory: Object of Research and Methods of Analysis. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*, 24(2), 35-40.

¹² Najmutdinova, D. K., Nurmukhamedova, L. S., Alieva, D. A., Maksudova, D. S., & Nosirova, Z. A. (2016). Study of the effects of the age at menopause and duration of menopause on bone mineral density in postmenopausal women in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Biomedicine*, 6(1), 38-40.

¹³ Pulatova Sabina. (2022). THE REVELATION OF VIRTUE THROUGH EVIL IN THE SHORT STORY "A FRIEND IN NEED" BY WILLIAM SOMERSET MAUGHAM. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnali*, 1(2), 240-244. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/100>

The article considers the correlation of the real facts and imagination in “Tamburlaine the Great” by Christopher Marlowe.¹⁴

This article discusses an attitude to women in the past and the interpretation of the image of women in the works of some writers.¹⁵

В современном обществе все более возрастает роль иностранных языков. Знание иностранного языка дает молодежи возможность приобщиться к мировой культуре, использовать в своей деятельности потенциал обширных ресурсов глобальной сети Интернет, а также работать с информационными и коммуникационными технологиями и мультимедийными средствами обучения.¹⁶

This article deals with the heroes of the novel “Between Two Doors”, one of the most popular works of modern Uzbek literature. There is a comprehensive analysis of the female image. A special place in the work of Utkir Khashimov is occupied by the novel “Between Two Doors”. The writer is concerned not only with the pressing social issues of today, but with eternal moral problems. In particular, by calling “Between Two Doors”, the writer means the path of person, which he walked from birth to death.¹⁷

Har bir millat madaniyatida kasallik nomlarini ifodalovchi qarashlar mavjud bo'lib ular shu xalq dunyoqarashini, dinini, urf-odatlarini, turmush tarzini va tarixini o'zida mujassamlashtiradi. Xususan, o'zbek va ingliz xalqi amaliy nutqida rak, sil, vabo kabi xavfli kasalliklar nomi qadimda tabulashtirilgan, bunga tarixiy sabablar mavjud. Hozirgi kunda ularning davosi topilgan bo'lsada, xalqimiz “yomon xastalik”, “og'ir dard”, “yomon kasallik” kabi birikmalarni qo'llash bilan kifoyalanadi.¹⁸

¹⁴ Temirovna, M. P. (2021). THE CORRELATION OF HISTORICAL TRUTH AND IMAGINATION IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE'S TRAGEDY “TAMBURLAINE THE GREAT”. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(12), 455-457.

¹⁵ Muradovich, R. M. (2021). The Image of a Woman in The Work of Uzbek Writers. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 3, 7-12.

¹⁶ Махмурова, М., Абдуллаева, Л. С., & Самадова, С. А. Современные методы преподавания иностранных языков. Коммуникативный метод. *Наука. Мысль*, 6, 72-76.

¹⁷ Turaeva, K., & Zarinabonu, A. (2022). Interpretation Of Woman Image in Modern Uzbek Literature (Based on Utkir Khashimov's Book “Between Two Doors”). *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 4, 42-44.

¹⁸ Baxronova Matluba. (2022). RUHIY KASALLIKLARNING INGLIZ ADABIYOTIDA BERILISHI.

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Badiiy adabiyotning qamrov darajasi keng sanaladi. Zero undagi janrlarning har biri insonning kamoloti uchun xizmat qiladi.¹⁹

В данной статье сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского.²⁰

В настоящее время глобальной социальной опасностью является угроза обнищания населения. Безработица, экономическая и социальная нестабильность, несбыточность надежд, крушение планов интенсифицируют процесс маргинализация населения.²¹

The relevance of speech and culture in the present day is considered important in linguistics and its areas of study are becoming more and more comprehensive day by day. This article will highlight the important aspects of the study of culture and national characteristics in the study of modern units of oral speech. Currently, English is widely spoken in the world community. It is the language of Advanced Science and technology, trade and cultural relations, trade and business.²²

The article is dedicated to the description of Uzbek national children's clothes of the past centuries and its modern implementation. Article describes types of clothes, its designation and modern usage.²³

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¹⁹ Oripova Kamola. (2022). O'ZBEK VA FRANSUZ TILLARIDAGI MAQOLLARDA JON KONSEPTINING IFODALANISHI. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(3), 398–408. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/209>

²⁰ Тухтаева, Ф. И., & Ҳамроева, Ш. Ш. (2019). Сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского. *Мировая наука*, (5), 709-713.

²¹ Суяров, З. Э. (2021). СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКОЕ ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ БЕДНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(12), 1175-1182.

²² NARZIYEVA, I. Z. (2021, March). COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE CULTURAL AND NATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MODERN UNITS OF ORAL SPEECH (based on Uzbek and English language materials). In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 285-289).

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